

Assisted Natural Regeneration of Hedges

www.af4eu.eu

An ANR hedge next to an agroforestry cereal field

Assisted natural regeneration (ANR) of hedges is an agro-ecological practice aimed at creating hedges without planting, by encouraging the natural regrowth of locally present species. The creation of a hedge by ANR is much less costly and time-consuming for the farmer than that of a conventional hedge, while offering the same ecological and landscape advantages, since it requires neither soil preparation nor planting. Moreover, the resulting vegetation, well adapted to the local context, is more resilient to climate change. Trees from natural seedlings have greater vigour and growth capacity than replanted seedlings. Seedlings may take one or more years to appear, but they will grow faster than in the nursery.

To create an ANR hedge, simply mark out an area the width of the hedge you want to create, where you will cease all intervention and avoid stepping. This means no agricultural machinery, no crushing, no mowing and no grazing. If livestock (including chickens) are present on the farm, it will be essential to fence off the area to ensure that they cannot enter during the hedge's formative years.

No maintenance is required for the formation of the hedge, other than to maintain the hedge within its perimeter. Depending on the grower's wishes, however, it is possible to protect the desired species from pests with protective sheaths, or to eliminate problematic species by regular pruning.

Tsoukalia Carpente

Ver de Terre Production

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.